

Nonlocal impulsive fractional and neutral equations with finite State-Dependent Delay

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Abstract

In this paper, we give sufficient conditions when the solution is depending on an finite delay to get the existence of mild solutions for two classes of Nonlocal impulsive fractional and neutral equations with finite State-Dependent Delay by using the nonlinear alternative of Frigon and Granas for contractions maps in Fréchet spaces. An example is provide to illustrate the theory.

Key words : impulsive semilinear functional equations, neutral problem, mild solution, state-dependent delay, nonlocal conditions, fixed point, fractional equations, nonlinear alternative, semigroup theory, Fréchet spaces, finite delay.

AMS Subject Classification : 26A33 - 34A12 - 34G20 - 34K37- 34K40 .

1 Introduction

In this paper, we give the existence of mild solutions defined on a positive real interval $I := [0, T]$ for two classes of first order impulsive semilinear functional and neutral functional evolution equations with state-dependent delay in a real separable Banach space $(E, |\cdot|)$ when the delay is finite.

Firstly, we present some preliminary concepts and results in Section 2 and then in Section 3 we study the following impulsive semilinear functional evolution equations with state-dependent delay

$${}^c D_0^\alpha y(t) = A(t)y(t) + f(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)}), \quad \text{a.e. } t \in I = [0, T] \quad (1)$$

$$y(t) + h_t(y) = \varphi(t), \quad t \in H := [-r, 0], \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta y|_{t=t_k} = I_k(y(t_k^-)) \quad k = 1, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

where $0 < r < +\infty$, $f : I \times C(H; E) \rightarrow E$, $\rho : I \times C(H; E) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\varphi \in C(H; E)$ and $h_t : C(H, E) \rightarrow E$ are given functions and $\{A(t)\}_{0 \leq t < +\infty}$ is a family of linear closed (not necessarily bounded) operators from E into E that generate an evolution system of operators $\{U(t, s)\}_{(t, s) \in J \times J}$ for $0 \leq s \leq t < +\infty$. $I_k : y \rightarrow y$, $0 < t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_m < t_{m+1} = T$. $\Delta y|_{t=t_k} = y(t_k^+) - y(t_k^-)$, $y(t_k^+) = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0^+} y(t_k + p)$ and

$y(t_k^-) = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0^-} y(t_k + p)$ represent respectively the right and the left limits of $y(t)$ at $t = t_k$.

We assume, as usual, in the theory of impulsive differential equations [16, 33, 45] that the solution of (1) – (3) is such that at the point of discontinuity t_k , $y(t_k) = y(t_k^-)$. Among the previous research, little is concerned with differential equations with fractional order and impulses. Recently, Benchohra et al. in [3, 20] establish sufficient conditions for the existence of solutions for a class of initial value problem for impulsive fractional differential equations involving the Caputo fractional derivative of order $0 < \alpha < 1$ and $1 < \alpha < 2$. In [15], B. Ahmad et al. give some existence results for two-point boundary value problems involving nonlinear impulsive hybrid differential equations of fractional order $1 < \alpha < 2$.

For any continuous function y defined on H and any $t \in I$, we denote by y_t the element of $C(H; E)$ defined by $y_t(\theta) = y(t + \theta)$ for $\theta \in H$. Here $y_t(\cdot)$ represents the history of the state from time $t - r$ up to the present time t .

Then, in Section 4, we consider the following impulsive neutral functional differential evolution equation with finite delay

$${}^c D_0^\alpha [y(t) - g(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)})] = A(t)y(t) + f(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)}), \quad \text{a.e. } t \in I, \quad (4)$$

$$y(t) + h_t = \varphi(t), \quad t \in H := [-r, 0], \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta y|_{t=t_k} = I_k(y(t_k^-)) \quad k = 1, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

where $A(\cdot)$, f and ϕ are as in problem (1) – (4) and $g : I \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is a given function. Finally in Section 5, two examples are given to illustrate the abstract theory.

Fractional differential equation are increasingly used for many mathematical models in science and engineering. In fact fractional differential equation are considered as an alternative model to nonlinear differential equation [35]. The theory of fractional differential equation has been extensively studied by several authors [36, 37, 40]. In [41, 42] the author have proved the existence of solution of abstract differential equation by using semigroup theory and fixed point theorem. Many partial fractional differential equation can be expressed as fractional differential equation in some Banach space [43]

Differential delay equations, or functional differential equations, have been used in modeling scientific phenomena for many years. Often, it has been assumed that the delay is either a fixed constant or is given as an integral in which case is called distributed delay; see for instance the books [29, 32, 50], and the papers [28, 23].

An extensive theory is developed for evolution equations [4, 5, 25]. Uniqueness and existence results have been established for different evolution problems in the papers by Baghli and Benchohra in [2], [9]-[15]. Recently, Wang *et al.* look for nonlinear fractional impulsive evolution equations in [46]-[49].

However, complicated situations in which the delay depends on the unknown functions have been proposed in modeling in recent years. These equations are frequently

called equations with state-dependent delay. Existence results and among other things were derived recently for functional differential equations when the solution is depending on the delay on a bounded interval for impulsive problems. We refer the reader to the papers by Abada *et al.* [1], Ait Dads and Ezzinbi [6], Anguraj *et al.* [7], Hernandez *et al.* [30] and Li *et al.* [34].

Byszewski is a first who study the nonlocal Cauchy problem for partial function evolution [21, 22]. Then, Benchohra and his collaborators considered various classes of problems with the nonlocal conditions in [18]-[19], Fu and Ezzinbi in [27], Li *et al.* in [38, 39] and Balachandran *et cie.* for various classes of nonlinear integrodifferential systems in [17].

Our main purpose in this paper is to extend some results from the cite literature devoted to state-dependent delay and those considered on a bounded interval for the evolution problems studied in [15]. We provide sufficient conditions for the existence of mild solutions on a positive real interval $J = [0, b]$ for the two classes of first order nonlocal perturbed semilinear functional and neutral functional evolution equations with state-dependent delay (1) – (3) and (4) – (6) with *state-dependent delay* when the delay is finite using the recent nonlinear alternative of Leray Schauder type due to Frigon and Granas for contractions maps in Fréchet spaces [26], combined with semigroup theory [5, 44].

2 Preliminaries

We introduce notations, definitions and theorems which are used throughout this paper.

Let $C([0, T]; E)$ be the space of continuous functions from $[0, T]$ into E and $B(E)$ be the space of all bounded linear operators from E into E , with the usual supremum norm

$$N \in B(E), \|N\|_{B(E)} = \sup \{ |N(y)| : |y| = 1 \}.$$

A measurable function $y : [0, +\infty) \rightarrow E$ is Bochner integrable if and only if $|y|$ is Lebesgue integrable. (For the Bochner integral properties, see the classical monograph of Yosida [51]).

Let $L^1([0, +\infty), E)$ denotes the Banach space of measurable functions $y : [0, +\infty) \rightarrow E$ which are Bochner integrable normed by

$$\|y\|_{L^1} = \int_0^{+\infty} |y(t)| dt.$$

In this paper, we will employ an axiomatic definition of the phase space \mathcal{B} introduced by Hale and Kato in [28] and follow the terminology used in [31]. Thus, $(\mathcal{B}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{B}})$ will be a seminormed linear space of functions mapping $(-\infty, 0]$ into E , and satisfying the following axioms :

(A₁) If $y : (-\infty, T) \rightarrow E, b > 0$, is continuous on $[0, b]$ and $y_0 \in \mathcal{B}$, then for every $t \in [0, b)$ the following conditions hold :

- (i) $y_t \in \mathcal{B}$;
- (ii) There exists a positive constant H such that $|y(t)| \leq H\|y_t\|_{\mathcal{B}}$;
- (iii) There exist two functions $K(\cdot), M(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ independent of y with K continuous and M locally bounded such that :

$$\|y_t\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq K(t) \sup\{|y(s)| : 0 \leq s \leq t\} + M(t)\|y_0\|_{\mathcal{B}}.$$

(A₂) For the function y in (A₁), y_t is a \mathcal{B} -valued continuous function on $[0, T]$.

(A₃) The space \mathcal{B} is complete.

Denote $K_T = \sup\{K(t) : t \in [0, T]\}$ and $M_T = \sup\{M(t) : t \in [0, T]\}$.

Remark 2.1 1. (ii) is equivalent to $|\phi(0)| \leq H\|\phi\|_{\mathcal{B}}$ for every $\phi \in \mathcal{B}$.

- 2. Since $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{B}}$ is a seminorm, two elements $\phi, \psi \in \mathcal{B}$ can verify $\|\phi - \psi\|_{\mathcal{B}} = 0$ without necessarily $\phi(\theta) = \psi(\theta)$ for all $\theta \leq 0$.
- 3. From the equivalence of in the first remark, we can see that for all $\phi, \psi \in \mathcal{B}$ such that $\|\phi - \psi\|_{\mathcal{B}} = 0$: We necessarily have that $\phi(0) = \psi(0)$.

We now indicate some examples of phase spaces. For other details we refer, for instance to the book by Hino *et al* [31].

Example 2.2 Let:

BC the space of bounded continuous functions defined from $(-\infty, 0]$ to E ;

BUC the space of bounded uniformly continuous functions defined from $(-\infty, 0]$ to E ;

$$C^\infty := \left\{ \phi \in BC : \lim_{\theta \rightarrow -\infty} \phi(\theta) \text{ exist in } E \right\};$$

$$C^0 := \left\{ \phi \in BC : \lim_{\theta \rightarrow -\infty} \phi(\theta) = 0 \right\}, \text{ endowed with the uniform norm}$$

$$\|\phi\| = \sup\{|\phi(\theta)| : \theta \leq 0\}.$$

We have that the spaces BUC , C^∞ and C^0 satisfy conditions (A₁) – (A₃). However, BC satisfies (A₁), (A₃) but (A₂) is not satisfied.

Example 2.3 The spaces C_g , UC_g , C_g^∞ and C_g^0 .

Let g be a positive continuous function on $(-\infty, 0]$. We define:

$$C_g := \left\{ \phi \in C((-\infty, 0], E) : \frac{\phi(\theta)}{g(\theta)} \text{ is bounded on } (-\infty, 0] \right\};$$

$C_g^0 := \left\{ \phi \in C_g : \lim_{\theta \rightarrow -\infty} \frac{\phi(\theta)}{g(\theta)} = 0 \right\}$, endowed with the uniform norm

$$\|\phi\| = \sup \left\{ \frac{|\phi(\theta)|}{g(\theta)} : \theta \leq 0 \right\}.$$

Then we have that the spaces C_g and C_g^0 satisfy conditions (A_3) . We consider the following condition on the function g .

$$(g_1) \text{ For all } a > 0, \sup_{0 \leq t \leq a} \sup \left\{ \frac{g(t+\theta)}{g(\theta)} : -\infty < \theta \leq -t \right\} < \infty.$$

They satisfy conditions (A_1) and (A_2) if (g_1) holds.

Example 2.4 The space C_γ .

For any real constant γ , we define the functional space C_γ by

$$C_\gamma := \left\{ \phi \in C((-\infty, 0], E) : \lim_{\theta \rightarrow -\infty} e^{\gamma\theta} \phi(\theta) \text{ exists in } E \right\}$$

endowed with the following norm

$$\|\phi\| = \sup \{ e^{\gamma\theta} |\phi(\theta)| : \theta \leq 0 \}.$$

Then in the space C_γ the axioms (A_1) – (A_3) are satisfied.

Definition 2.5 A function $f : J \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is said to be an L^1 -Carathéodory function if it satisfies :

- (i) for each $t \in I$ the function $f(t, \cdot) : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is continuous ;
- (ii) for each $y \in \mathcal{B}$ the function $f(\cdot, y) : J \rightarrow E$ is measurable ;
- (iii) for every positive integer k there exists $h_k \in L^1(I; \mathbb{R}^+)$ such that

$$|f(t, y)| \leq h_k(t) \quad \text{for all } \|y\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq k \quad \text{and almost every } t \in I.$$

In what follows, we assume that $\{A(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$ is a family of closed densely defined linear unbounded operators on the Banach space E and with domain $D(A(t))$ independent of t . Additionally, we introduce following hypothesis:

- (P1) For $t \in [0, T]$ The domain $D(A(t)) = D$ is independent of t and is dense on X .
- (P2) For $t \geq 0$, the resolvent $R(\lambda, A(t)) = (\lambda I - A(t))^{-1}$ exists for all λ with $\operatorname{Re}(\lambda) \leq 0$, and there is a constant M independent of λ and t such that

$$\|R(t, A(t))\| \leq M(1 + |\lambda|)^{-1} \quad \text{pour } \operatorname{Re}(\lambda) \leq 0.$$

(P3) There exist constant $L > 0$ and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ such that

$$\|A(t) - A(\theta)A^{-1}(\tau)\| \leq L|t - \tau|^\alpha \quad t, \theta, \tau \in I.$$

(P4) The resolvent $R(t, A(t))(t \geq 0)$ is compact.

Lemma 2.6 ([4], p.159) Under the assumption (P1) – (P4), the Cauchy problem

$$y'(t) - A(t)y(t) = 0 \quad t \in I : y(0) = y_0,$$

has a unique evolution system $\{U(t, s) / 0 \leq \theta \leq t \leq T\}$ on E satisfying the following properties:

1. $U(t, t) = I$ where I is the identity operator in E ,
2. $U(t, s)U(s, \tau) = U(t, \tau)$ for $0 \leq \tau \leq s \leq t < +\infty$,
3. $U(t, s) \in B(E)$ the space of bounded linear operators on E , where for every $(t, s) \in \Delta$ and for each $y \in E$, the mapping $(t, s) \rightarrow U(t, s)y$ is continuous.
4. For $0 \leq \theta \leq t \leq T$, $U(t, s) : X \rightarrow D$ and $t \rightarrow U(t, s)$ is strongly differentiable on E . The derivative $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}U(t, s) \in B(E)$ and it is strongly continuous on $0 \leq \theta \leq t \leq T$. Moreover,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}U(t, s) = A(t)U(t, s) \quad \text{for } 0 \leq \theta \leq t \leq T,$$

$$\left\| \frac{\partial}{\partial t}U(t, s) \right\|_{B(E)} = \|A(t)U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} \leq \frac{C}{t - \theta},$$

$$\|A(t)U(t, s)A^{-1}(s)\|_{B(E)} \leq C \quad \text{for } 0 \leq \theta \leq t \leq T.$$

5. For every $v \in D$ and $t \in (0, T]$, $U(t, s)v$ is differentiable with respect to θ on $0 \leq \theta \leq t \leq T$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s}U(t, s)v = -U(t, s)A(s)v.$$

6. $U(t, s)$ is compact operator for $0 \leq \theta \leq t \leq T$.

And, for each $y_0 \in E$, the Cauchy problem has a unique classical solution $y \in C^1(I, E)$ given by

$$y(t) = U(t, 0)y_0, \quad t \in I$$

More details on evolution systems and their properties could be found on the books of Ahmed [4], Engel and Nagel [24] and Pazy [44].

The nonlocal condition $y(t) + h_t(y) = \varphi(t)$ for $t \in [-r, 0]$ can be applied in physics with better effect than the classical initial condition $y(0) = y_0$.

For example, $h_t(y)$ may be given by

$$h_t(y) = \sum_{i=1}^p c_i y(t_i + t), \quad t \in H$$

where c_i , $i = 1, \dots, p$ are given constants and $0 < t_1 < \dots < t_p < +\infty$.

At time $t = 0$, we have

$$h_0(y) = \sum_{i=1}^p c_i y(t_i).$$

Let X be a Fréchet space with a family of semi-norms $\{\|\cdot\|_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. We assume that the family of semi-norms $\{\|\cdot\|_n\}$ verifies :

$$\|x\|_1 \leq \|x\|_2 \leq \|x\|_3 \leq \dots \quad \text{for every } x \in X.$$

Let $Y \subset X$, we say that Y is bounded if for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists $\overline{M}_n > 0$ such that

$$\|y\|_n \leq \overline{M}_n \quad \text{for all } y \in Y.$$

To X we associate a sequence of Banach spaces $\{(X^n, \|\cdot\|_n)\}$ as follows : For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we consider the equivalence relation \sim_n defined by : $x \sim_n y$ if and only if $\|x - y\|_n = 0$ for $x, y \in X$. We denote $X^n = (X/\sim_n, \|\cdot\|_n)$ the quotient space, the completion of X^n with respect to $\|\cdot\|_n$. To every $Y \subset X$, we associate a sequence $\{Y^n\}$ of subsets $Y^n \subset X^n$ as follows : For every $x \in X$, we denote $[x]_n$ the equivalence class of x of subset X^n and we defined $Y^n = \{[x]_n : x \in Y\}$. We denote \overline{Y}^n , $\text{int}_n(Y^n)$ and $\partial_n Y^n$, respectively, the closure, the interior and the boundary of Y^n with respect to $\|\cdot\|_n$ in X^n . The corresponding nonlinear alternative result is as follows

Theorem 2.7 (Nonlinear Alternative of Granas-Frigon, [26]). *Let X be a Fréchet space and $Y \subset X$ a closed subset and let $N : Y \rightarrow X$ be a contraction such that $N(Y)$ is bounded. Then one of the following statements holds :*

(C1) N has a unique fixed point ;

(C2) There exists $\lambda \in [0, 1)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x \in \partial_n Y^n$ such that $\|x - \lambda N(x)\|_n = 0$.

Let us recall the following known definitions. For more details see.

Definition 2.8 *The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\alpha > 0$ of a function $f : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of order $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ is defined as by*

$$I_0^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s) ds \quad (7)$$

Provide the right hand side exists pointwise on \mathbb{R}^+ . $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Euler gamma function. For instance, $I^\alpha f$ exists for all $\alpha > 0$. When $h \in C^0(\mathbb{R}^+) \cap L_{loc}^1(\mathbb{R}^+)$: note also that when $h \in C^0(\mathbb{R}_0^+)$ then $I^\alpha f \in C^0(\mathbb{R}_0^+)$ and moreover $I^\alpha f(0) = 0$

Definition 2.9 The fractional derivative of order $\alpha > 0$ of a function $f : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in the caputo sense is given by

$$\frac{d^\alpha f(t)}{dt^\alpha} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dt} \int_a^t (t-s)^{m-\alpha-1} f(s) ds = \frac{d}{dt} I_a^{1-\alpha} f(t)$$

3 Semilinear Evolution Equations

Before stating and proving the main result, we give first the definition of a mild solution of the perturbed semilinear evolution problem (1) – (3).

Lemma 3.1 The system (1) – (3) is equivalent to the nonlinear integral equation

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) = & \varphi(0) - h_0(y) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} A(s)y(s) ds \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds \\ & + \sum_{0 < t_k < t} I_k(x(t_k^-)) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In other words, every solution of the integral equation (8) is also solution of the system (1) – (3) and vice versa.

Proof. It can be proved by applying the integral operator to both sides of the system (1) – (3), and using some classical results from fractional calculus to get (8).

Definition 3.2 We say that the function $y(\cdot) : [-r, T] \rightarrow E$ is a mild solution of (1) – (3) if $y(t) + h_t(y) = \varphi(t)$ for all $t \in H$ and y satisfies the following integral equation

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) = & U(t, 0) [\varphi(0) - h_0(y)] + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t-s)^{\alpha-1} u(t, s) f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(t, s) f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds \\ & + \sum_{0 < t_k < t} I_k(x(t_k^-)) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Now let us consider the set functions

$$PC(I, E) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} y : I \rightarrow E : y \in C([t_k, t_{k+1}], E) \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, m \quad \text{and there exists } x(t_k^-) \\ \text{and } y(t_k^+), k = 1, \dots, m \quad \text{with } y(t_k^-) = y(t_k) \end{array} \right\}$$

Endowed with the norm

$$\|y\|_{PC} = \sup_{t \in I} \|y(t)\| = \|\mu\|_{PC}$$

$(PC(I, E), \|\cdot\|_{PC})$ is Banach space.

Set

$$\mathcal{R}(\rho^-) = \{\rho(s, \varphi) : (s, \varphi) \in I \times C(H; E), \rho(s, \varphi) \leq 0\}.$$

We always assume that $\rho : I \times C(H; E) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous. Additionally, we introduce following hypothesis:

(H_φ) The function $t \rightarrow \varphi_t$ is continuous from $\mathcal{R}(\rho^-)$ into $C(H; E)$ and there exists a continuous and bounded function $\mathcal{L}^\varphi : \mathcal{R}(\rho^-) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ such that

$$\|\varphi_t\| \leq \mathcal{L}^\varphi(t) \|\varphi\| \quad \text{for every } t \in \mathcal{R}(\rho^-).$$

Remark 3.3 *The condition (H_φ), is frequently verified by continuous and bounded functions. For more details, see for instance [31].*

We will need to introduce the following hypothesis which are assumed thereafter

(H0) $U(t, s)$ is compact for $t - s > 0$.

(H1) There exists a constant $\widehat{M} \geq 1$ such that

$$\|U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} \leq \widehat{M} \quad \text{for every } (t, s) \in \Delta.$$

(H2) There exists a function $p, q \in L^1_{loc}(I; \mathbb{R}_+)$ such that :

$$|f(t, u)| \leq p(t) + q(t) \|u\|_B \quad \text{for a.e. } t \in J \text{ and each } u \in C(H; E).$$

(H3) For all $R > 0$, there exists $l_R \in L^1_{loc}(J; \mathbb{R}_+)$ such that :

$$|f(t, u) - f(t, v)| \leq l_R(t) \|u - v\|$$

for all $u, v \in C(H; E)$ with $\|u\| \leq R$ and $\|v\| \leq R$.

(H4) there exists $\sigma > 0$ such that

$$|h_t(u)| \leq \sigma$$

for each $u \in C(H, E)$ and $t \in I$.

(H5) $\|I_k(y)\| \leq \rho_1$

For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we define in $C([-r, T]; E)$ the semi-norms by :

$$\|y\|_n := \sup \{ |y(t)| : t \in [0, n] \}$$

Lemma 3.4 ([30], Lemma 2.4)

If $y : [-r, T] \rightarrow E$ is a function such that $y_0 = \varphi$, then

$$\|y_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq (M_T + \mathcal{L}^\varphi)\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + K_T \sup\{|y(\theta)|; \theta \in [0, \max\{0, s\}]\}, \quad s \in \mathcal{R}(\rho^-) \cup I,$$

where $\mathcal{L}^\varphi = \sup_{t \in \mathcal{R}(\rho^-)} \mathcal{L}^\varphi(t)$.

Theorem 3.5 Assume that (H_φ) , and $(H0) - (H8)$ hold and moreover for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, hold and moreover

$$\left(\frac{\widehat{M}l_n^*(m+1)t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M}\rho m \right) < 1 \tag{10}$$

Where $p^* = \sup p(s)$, $q^* = \sup q(s)$ and . Then the problem (1) – (3) has a unique mild solution on $(-\infty, T]$. Then the problem (1) – (3) has a mild solution on $(-\infty, T]$.

Proof. We transform the problem (1) – (3) into a fixed-point problem. Consider the operator $N : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ defined by

$$N(y)(t) = \begin{cases} \varphi(0) - h_0(y), & \text{if } t \in H; \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(t,s) f(s, y_{\rho(s,y_s)}) ds, \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(t,s) f(s, y_{\rho(s,y_s)}) ds \\ + \sum_{0 < t_k < t} I_k(x(t_k^-)) & \text{if } t \in I. \end{cases}$$

Clearly, fixed points of the operator N are mild solutions of the problem (1) – (3).

$$\begin{aligned} |Ny(t)| &\leq \|U(t,0)\|_{B(E)}|\varphi(0) - h_0(y)| \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t,s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s,y_s)})| ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t,s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s,y_s)})| ds. \\ &+ \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \|u(t_k, s)I_k y(t_k^-)\| \\ &\leq \widehat{M}(\|\varphi\| + \sigma) + \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} [p(s) + q(s)\|y_{\rho(s,y_s)}\|] ds \\ &+ \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} [p(s) + q(s)\|y_{\rho(s,y_s)}\|] ds + \widehat{M}\rho_1 m \end{aligned}$$

It's follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 |Ny(t)| &\leq \widehat{M}(\|\varphi\| + \sigma) + \frac{\widehat{M}p^*t^\alpha(m+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M}\rho_1m \\
 &+ \frac{\widehat{M}q^*}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} (|y(s)| + \mathcal{L}^\varphi\|\varphi\|)ds + \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} (|y(s)| + \mathcal{L}^\varphi\|\varphi\|)ds \right] \\
 &\leq \widehat{M}(\|\varphi\| + \sigma) + \frac{\widehat{M}t^\alpha(m+1)[p^* + \mathcal{L}^\varphi]\|\varphi\|q^*}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M}\rho_1m \\
 &+ \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} (|y(s)|)ds + \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} |y(s)|ds \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Let y be a possible solution of the problem (1) – (3). Given $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $t \leq n$, then from (H0) – (H5), (H $_\varphi$) and Lemma 3.4, we have for each $t \in [0, n]$ we suppose that

$$\delta_n = \widehat{M}(\|\varphi\| + \sigma) + \frac{\widehat{M}t^\alpha(m+1)[p^* + L^\varphi\|\varphi\|q^*]}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M}\rho_1m$$

It's follows that

$$|N(y(t))| \leq \delta_n + \frac{\widehat{M}q^*\|\mu\|_{PC}(m+1)t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} = \delta$$

$$|N(y(t))| \leq \delta$$

Since $\|y\|_n \leq \delta$, we have $\|y\|_n \leq \max \delta, \|\varphi\| := \Theta_n$. Since for every $t \in [0, T]$, we have $\|y\|_n \leq \max \delta, \|\varphi\| := \Theta_n$.

Set

$$Y = \{ y \in C([-r, T]; E) : \sup\{|y(t)| : 0 \leq t \leq n\} \leq \Theta_n + 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \}.$$

Clearly, Y is a closed subset of $C([-r, T]; E)$.

We shall show that $N : Y \rightarrow C([-r, T]; E)$ is a contraction operator. Indeed, consider $y, \bar{y} \in Y$, thus using (H1) and (H3), (H6) for each $t \in [0, n]$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ Using (H $_\varphi$) and Lemma 3.4, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
|N(y)(t) - N(\bar{y})(t)| &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) - f(s, \bar{y}_{\rho(s, \bar{y}_s)})| ds \\
&+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) - f(s, \bar{y}_{\rho(s, \bar{y}_s)})| ds \\
&+ \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \|u(t_k, s)\| \|I_k(y(t_k^-)) - I_k(\bar{y}(t_k^-))\| \\
&\leq \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) \|y_{\rho(s, y_s)} - \bar{y}_{\rho(s, \bar{y}_s)}\| ds \right. \\
&+ \left. \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) \|y_{\rho(s, y_s)} - \bar{y}_{\rho(s, \bar{y}_s)}\| ds \right] \\
&+ \widehat{M} \sum_{k=1}^m \|y(t_k^-) - \bar{y}(t_k^-)\| \\
&\leq \frac{\widehat{M} l_n^*}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) |y(s) - \bar{y}(s)| ds \\
&+ \frac{\widehat{M} l_n^*}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) |y(s) - \bar{y}(s)| ds \\
&+ \widehat{M} m \rho \|y - \bar{y}\| \\
&\leq \left(\frac{\widehat{M} l_n^* (m+1) t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M} \rho m \right) \|y - \bar{y}\|
\end{aligned}$$

So, the operator N is a contraction for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. From the choice of Y there is no $y \in \partial Y^n$ such that $y = \lambda N(y)$, $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. Then the statement (C2) in Theorem 2.7 does not hold. The nonlinear alternative of Frigon and Granas shows that (C1) holds. Thus, we deduce that the operator N has a unique fixed-point y^* which is the unique mild solution of the problem (1) – (3).

4 Semilinear Neutral Evolution Equations

Before stating and proving the main result, we give first the definition of a mild solution of the perturbed semilinear evolution problem (4) – (6).

Lemma 4.1 *The system (4) – (6) is equivalent to the nonlinear integral equation*

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) = & [\varphi(0) - h_0(y) - g(0, \varphi)] + g(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)}) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} A(s) y(s) ds \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds \\ & + \sum_{0 < t_k < t} I_k(x(t_k^-)) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In other words, every solution of the integral equation (8) is also solution of the system (4) – (6) and vice versa.

Proof. It can be proved by applying the integral operator to both sides of the system (4) – (6), and using some classical results from fractional calculus to get (8).

Definition 4.2 *We say that the function $y : [-r, T] \rightarrow E$ is a mild solution of (4) – (6) if $y(t) = \varphi(t)$ for all $t \in H$ and y satisfies the following integral equation*

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) = & U(t, 0) [\varphi(0) - h_0(y) - g(0, \varphi)] \\ & + g(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)}) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t-s)^{\alpha-1} u(t, s) f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(t, s) f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds \\ & + \sum_{0 < t_k < t} I_k(x(t_k^-)) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

We consider the hypotheses (H_φ) , lemma and $(H0) - (H2)$, $(H4) - (H5)$ and we will need the following assumptions

$(H6)$ There exists a constant $R_n > 0$ such that

$$|g(s, \varphi) - g(\bar{s}, \bar{\varphi})| \leq R_n \|\varphi - \bar{\varphi}\|_B$$

for all $\varphi, \bar{\varphi} \in C(H, E)$.

$(H7)$ The function g is completely continuous and for any bounded set $Q \subset \mathcal{B}$ the set $\{t \rightarrow g(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)})\}$ is equicontinuous in $C(I, E)$.

$(H8)$ $\|y(t_k^-) - \bar{y}(t_k^-)\| \leq \rho \|y - \bar{y}\|$

Theorem 4.3 *Suppose that hypotheses (H_φ) , $(H0) - (H2)$, $(H4)$ and $(H5) - (H6)$ are satisfied hold and moreover*

$$\left(\frac{\widehat{M}_n^* (m+1) t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M} \rho m + R_n \right) < 1 \quad (13)$$

Where $p^* = \sup p(s)$, $q^* = \sup q(s)$. Then the problem (4) – (6) has a unique mild solution on $(-\infty, T]$. Then the problem (4) – (6) has a mild solution.

Proof. Consider the operator $\tilde{N} : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ defined by

$$N(y)(t) = \begin{cases} [\varphi(0) - h_0(y) - g(0, \varphi) + g(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)}), & \text{if } t \in H; \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(t, s) f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds, \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(t, s) f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) ds \\ + \sum_{0 < t_k < t} I_k(x(t_k^-)) & \text{if } t \in I. \end{cases}$$

Clearly, the fixed points of the operator \tilde{N} are mild solutions of the problem (4) – (6).

Let y be a possible solution of the problem (4) – (6). Given $n \in \mathcal{N}$ and $t \leq n$. Then, using (H1) – (H5), (H_φ) and Lemma 3.4, we have for each $t \in [0, n]$

$$\begin{aligned} |Ny(t)| &\leq \|U(t, 0)\|_{B(E)} |\varphi(0) - h_0(y)_g(0, \varphi)| + g(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)}) \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)})| ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)})| ds. \\ &+ \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \|u(t_k, s) I_k y(t_k^-)\| \\ &\leq \widehat{M}((R_n + 1)\|\varphi\| + \sigma) \\ &+ R_n \|y_{\rho(t, y_t)}\| + \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} [p(s) + q(s)\|y_{\rho(s, y_s)}\|] ds \\ &+ \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} [p(s) + q(s)\|y_{\rho(s, y_s)}\|] ds + \widehat{M}\rho_1 m \end{aligned}$$

Since $\|y_{\rho(t, y_t)}\| \leq |y(t)| + \mathcal{L}^\varphi \|\varphi\|$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |Ny(t)| &\leq \widehat{M}((R_n + 1)\|\varphi\| + \sigma) + \frac{\widehat{M}p^*t^\alpha(m+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \\ &+ \frac{\widehat{M}q^*}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} (|y(s)| + \mathcal{L}^\varphi \|\varphi\|) ds \right. \\ &+ \left. \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} (|y(s)| + \mathcal{L}^\varphi \|\varphi\|) ds \right] + \widehat{M}\rho_1 m + \mathcal{L}^\varphi \|\varphi\| + R_n |y(t)| \\ &\leq \widehat{M}((R_n + 1)\|\varphi\| + \sigma) + \widehat{M}\rho_1 m + \mathcal{L}^\varphi \|\varphi\| + R_n \|\mu\|_{PC} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\widehat{M}t^\alpha(m+1)[p^* + \mathcal{L}^\varphi\|\varphi\|q^*]}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M}\rho_1m \\
& + \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} (|y(s)|)ds + \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} |y(s)|ds \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Let y be a possible solution of the problem (4) – (6). Given $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $t \leq n$, then from (H1) – (H8), (H_φ) and Lemma 3.4, we have for each $t \in [0, n]$

we suppose that

$$\delta_n = \widehat{M}((R_n + 1)\|\varphi\| + \sigma) + \frac{\widehat{M}t^\alpha(m+1)[p^* + L^\varphi\|\varphi\|q^*]}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + L^\varphi\|\varphi\| + \widehat{M}\rho_1m$$

It's follows that

$$|N(y(t))| \leq \delta_n + \frac{\widehat{M}q^*\|\mu\|_{PC}(m+1)t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + R_n\|\mu\|_{PC} = \delta$$

$$|N(y(t))| \leq \delta$$

Since $\|y\|_n \leq \delta$, we have $\|y\|_n \leq \max\{\delta, \|\varphi\|\} := \Theta_n$. Since for every $t \in [0, T]$, we have $\|y\|_n \leq \max\{\delta, \|\varphi\|\} := \Theta_n$.

Set

$$Y = \{ y \in C([-r, T]; E) : \sup\{|y(t)| : 0 \leq t \leq n\} \leq \Theta_n + 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \}.$$

Clearly, Y is a closed subset of $C([-r, T]; E)$.

Since $\|y\|_n \leq \mu(t)$, we have $\|y\|_n \leq \max\{\|\varphi\|, \Lambda_n\} := \Theta_n$.

Now, we shall show that $\tilde{N} : Y \rightarrow C([-r, T]; E)$ is a contraction operator. Indeed, consider $y, \bar{y} \in Y$, thus for each $t \in [0, n]$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\begin{aligned}
|N(y)(t) - N(\bar{y})(t)| &\leq |g(t, y_{\rho(t, y_t)}) - g(t, \bar{y}_{\rho(t, y_t)})| \\
&+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) - f(s, \bar{y}_{\rho(s, \bar{y}_s)})| ds \\
&+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} \|U(t, s)\|_{B(E)} |f(s, y_{\rho(s, y_s)}) - f(s, \bar{y}_{\rho(s, \bar{y}_s)})| ds \\
&+ \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \|u(t_k, s)\| \|I_k(y(t_k^-)) - I_k(\bar{y}(t_k^-))\| \\
&\leq R_n \|y_{\rho(t, y_t)} - \bar{y}_{\rho(t, y_t)}\|_n \\
&+ \frac{\widehat{M}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) \|y_{\rho(s, y_s)} - \bar{y}_{\rho(s, y_s)}\| ds \right. \\
&+ \left. \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) \|y_{\rho(s, y_s)} - \bar{y}_{\rho(s, y_s)}\| ds \right] \\
&+ \widehat{M} \sum_{k=1}^m \|y(t_k^-) - \bar{y}(t_k^-)\|
\end{aligned}$$

Using (H_φ) and Lemma 3.4, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
|\tilde{N}(y)(t) - \tilde{N}(\bar{y})(t)| &\leq R_n \|y - \bar{y}\|_n \\
&+ \frac{\widehat{M} l_n^*}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \sum_{0 < t_k < t} \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (t_k - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) |y(s) - \bar{y}(s)| ds \\
&+ \frac{\widehat{M} l_n^*}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_k}^t (t - s)^{\alpha-1} l_n(s) |y(s) - \bar{y}(s)| ds \\
&+ \widehat{M} m \rho \|y - \bar{y}\| \\
&\leq \left(\frac{\widehat{M} l_n^* (m+1) t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M} \rho m + R_n \right) \|y - \bar{y}\|
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\|\tilde{N}(y) - \tilde{N}(\bar{y})\|_n \leq \left(\frac{\widehat{M}l_n^*(m+1)t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M}\rho m + R_n \right) \|y - \bar{y}\|_n.$$

So, for an appropriate choice of L_n^* and t^α such that

$$\left[\frac{\widehat{M}l_n^*(m+1)t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \widehat{M}\rho m + R_n \right] < 1,$$

the operator \tilde{N} is a contraction for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. From the choice of Y there is no $y \in \partial Y^n$ such that $y = \lambda \tilde{N}(y)$ for some $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. Then the statement (C2) in Theorem 2.7 does not hold. A consequence of the nonlinear alternative of Frigon and Granas shows that (C1) holds. We deduce that the operator \tilde{N} has a unique fixed-point y^* which is the unique mild solution of the problem (4) – (6).

5 Examples

To illustrate the previous results, we give in this section two examples.

Example 1. Consider the partial functional differential equation

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & {}^c D_0^\alpha u(t, \xi) = \frac{\partial^2 u(t, \xi)}{\partial \xi^2} + a_0(t, \xi)u(t, \xi) \\ & + \int_{-r}^0 a_1(s-t)u \left[s - \rho_1(t)\rho_2 \left(\int_0^\pi a_2(\theta)|u(t, \theta)|^2 d\theta \right), \xi \right] ds \\ & + \int_{-r}^0 a_3(s-t)u \left[s - \rho_1(t)\rho_2 \left(\int_0^\pi a_2(\theta)|u(t, \theta)|^2 d\theta \right), \xi \right] ds, \\ & \hspace{20em} \xi \in [0, \pi], \hspace{2em} (14) \\ & u(t, 0) = u(t, \pi) = 0, \hspace{15em} 0 \leq t \leq b, \\ & u(\theta, \xi) + \bar{h}_\theta(u) = u_0(\theta, \xi), \hspace{5em} -r < \theta \leq 0, \xi \in [0, \pi], \\ & \Delta U|_{t=\frac{T}{2}} = I_1(\frac{T}{2}) \end{aligned} \right.$$

Where $a_0(t, \xi)$ is a continuous functions and uniformly Hölder continuous in t , $0 < \alpha < 1$; $a_1, a_3 : [-r, 0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, a_2 : [0, \pi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \rho : [0, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, for $i = 1, 2$; $\bar{h}_\theta : E \rightarrow C(H, E)$ $I_1 : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous functions given.

To study this system, we consider the space $E = L^2([0, \pi], \mathbb{R})$ and the operator $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ given by $Aw = w''$ with

$$D(A) := \{ w \in E : w'' \in E, w(0) = w(\pi) = 0 \}$$

It is well known that A is the infinitesimal generator of an analytic semigroup $\{T(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$ on E , with compact resolvent. On the domain $D(A)$, we define the operators $A(t) : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ by

$$A(t)x(\xi) = Ax(\xi) + a_0(t, \xi)x(\xi).$$

By assuming that $a_0(\cdot)$ is continuous and that $a_0(t, \xi) \leq -\delta_0$ ($\delta_0 > 0$) for every $t \in \mathbb{R}$, $\xi \in [0, \pi]$, and specific case $\alpha = 1$ it follows that the system

$$u'(t) = A(t)u(t) \quad t \geq s,$$

$$u(s) = x \in E,$$

has an associated evolution family given by

$$U(t, s)x(\xi) = \left[T(t-s) \exp \left(\int_s^t a_0(\tau, \xi) d\tau \right) x \right] (\xi).$$

From this expression, it follows that $U(t, s)$ is a compact linear operator and that

$$\|U(t, s)\| \leq e^{-(1+\delta_0)(t-s)} \text{ for every } (t, s) \in \Delta.$$

Theorem 5.1 *Let $\varphi \in C(H, E)$. Assume that condition (H_φ) holds, $\rho_i : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, 2$, are continuous and the functions $a_1, a_3 : \mathbb{R}_- \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $a_2 : [0, \pi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous. Then there exists a mild solution of (14) on $] -\infty, b]$.*

Proof. From the assumptions, we have that

$$f(t, \psi)(\xi) = \int_{-r}^0 a_1(s) \psi(s, \xi) ds,$$

$$\rho(s, \psi) = s - \rho_1(s) \rho_2 \left(\int_0^\pi a_2(\theta) |\psi(0, \xi)|^2 d\theta \right),$$

are well defined functions, which permit to transform system (14) into the abstract system (1) – (2). Moreover, the function f and h is bounded linear operator. Now, the existence of mild solutions can be deduced from a direct application of Theorem 3.5. From Remark 3.3, we have the following result

Corollary 5.2 *Let $\varphi \in C(H, E)$ be continuous and bounded. Then there exists a mild solution of (14) on $] -\infty, b]$.*

Example 2. Consider the semilinear neutral evolution equation

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & {}^c D_0^\alpha \left[u(t, \xi) - \int_{-r}^0 a_3(s-t) u \left(s - \rho_1(t) \rho_2 \left(\int_0^\pi a_2(\theta) |u(t, \theta)|^2 d\theta \right), \xi \right) ds \right] \\ & = \frac{\partial^2 u(t, \xi)}{\partial \xi^2} + a_0(t, \xi) u(t, \xi) \\ & + \int_{-r}^0 a_1(s-t) u \left(s - \rho_1(t) \rho_2 \left(\int_0^\pi a_2(\theta) |u(t, \theta)|^2 d\theta \right), \xi \right) ds \\ & + \int_{-r}^0 a_4(s-t) u \left(s - \rho_1(t) \rho_2 \left(\int_0^\pi a_2(\theta) |u(t, \theta)|^2 d\theta \right), \xi \right) ds, \\ & \hspace{20em} , \xi \in [0, \pi], \\ & v(t, 0) = v(t, \pi) = 0, \hspace{10em} 0 \leq t \leq b, \\ & v(\theta, \xi) + \bar{h}_\theta(u) = v_0(\theta, \xi), \hspace{5em} -r < \theta \leq 0, \xi \in [0, \pi]. \\ & \Delta U|_{t=\frac{T}{2}} = I_1(\frac{T}{2}) \end{aligned} \right. \tag{15}$$

$a_4 : \mathbb{R}_- \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function.

Theorem 5.3 Let $\varphi \in C(H, E)$. Assume that condition (H_φ) holds, $d : [0, \pi] \rightarrow E$, $\rho_i : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for $i = 1, 2$, $a_1, a_3, a_4 : \mathbb{R}_- \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $a_2 : [0, \pi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ $I_1 : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous. Then there exists a mild solution of (15) on $]-\infty, b]$.

Proof. From the assumptions, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, \psi)(\xi) &= \int_{-r}^0 a_1(s) \psi(s, \xi) ds, \\ g(t, \psi)(\xi) &= \int_{-r}^0 a_3(s) \psi(s, \xi) ds, \\ \rho(s, \psi) &= s - \rho_1(s) \rho_2 \left(\int_0^\pi a_2(\theta) |\psi(0, \xi)|^2 d\theta \right), \end{aligned}$$

are well defined functions, which permit to transform system (15) into the abstract system (4) – (5). Moreover, the function f, g and h is bounded linear operator. Now, the existence of mild solutions can be deduced from a direct application of Theorem 4.3.

From Remark 3.3, we have the following result

Corollary 5.4 Let $\varphi \in C(H, E)$ be continuous and bounded. Then there exists a mild solution of (15) on $]-\infty, b]$.

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